
Weather-induced emergency situations: Extreme data in situational awareness and visualisation

Iris Gräßler⁽¹⁾, Jens Pottebaum⁽¹⁾, Michael Hieb⁽¹⁾, Sylvia Pratzler-Wanczura⁽²⁾,
Oliver Krüger⁽²⁾, Ivana Kruijff⁽³⁾ und Nicola Rupp⁽³⁾

(1) Paderborn University

(2) Dortmund Firebrigade, Institute for Fire and Rescue technology

(3) Deutsches Rettungsrobotik-Zentrum

Abstract

Extreme weather situations increasingly lead to hazardous situations with high demands on decision-making and communication. Weather and impact forecasts serve to prepare for such an emergency situation, and extreme data must be processed during operations. Therefore, extreme data is categorised with reference to global weather data and data from local situation reconnaissance using sensors carried by mobile robots. A concept is presented in which information quality is explicitly considered in visualization for situational awareness. This extends existing principles of information visualisation with regard to the uncertainty resulting from extreme data. The results are intended to help decision-makers at different management levels to make informed decisions.

Introduction

Climate change becomes perceivable, among other things, through changed weather and increasing extreme weather situations, such as those that occurred in Western Europe in 2021 (Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat und Bundesministerium der Finanzen 2021). The term “extreme weather” should be understood here in the sense of “weather with potentially extreme effects”. Thus, on the one hand, there is a need for long-term preparation and prevention (e. g., (Deutscher Wetterdienst et al. 2020)), or, on the other hand, an acute situation that must be treated as an emergency situation evolving over time. This results in high demands on decision-making and communication (Terti et al. 2019) as well as self-protection of the population (Gräßler et al. 2018). Weather forecasts and impact forecasts serve to prepare for such a hazard situation (e. g., (Sutanto et al. 2019)). In this article, extreme data is categorised, which in particular addresses the differentiation of global and local data in situational awareness including data from sensors carried by mobile robots. To this end, the basics are first developed and presented with reference to applications. Interdependencies with regard to information quality are derived

and transferred into requirements for situation visualisation. In this way, existing basics of information visualisation are extended with regard to the uncertainty resulting from extreme data. The results can be used in all forms of geo-based situation and command information systems

Foundations

Stationary and mobile sensor systems that collect data limited to a local area are used in hazard prevention. Examples are weather stations and river gauges, but also airborne and ground-based robotic systems (UAV/UGV, see Figure 1). There are different types of data to be collected there. In the case of weather stations, these are time series from different sensors. In the case of UAV and UGV, a higher variance is possible by equipping the robots with sensors (Kruijff-Korbayova et al. 2021). With a view to optimal flight characteristics and maximum utilisation of payload, UAVs often operate integrated systems that provide, for example, video streams (H-264, MPEG-4) and photo data. However, as with UGV, configurable systems are also available here, which include, for example, thermal imaging cameras, laser scanners and hazardous material sensors. On the robotic platforms, pre-processing of streams is partly possible, so that time series or point clouds are sent in data formats such as GeoTIFF, obj or ply. Data partly refers to the actual situation in high resolution, whereby latencies in the communication have to be considered. In the case of moving sensor systems, data from the robot platform itself can also be included, describing, for example, position, orientation, joint angle or acceleration (Inertial Measurement Units, odometry) and extending measurement data with context metadata. All systems transmit with time stamps; however, synchronisation to determine a common "now" is technically challenging and can be crucial in calculations.

Figure 1 Collection of local data, for example by Unmanned Aerial or Ground Vehicles (UAV/UGV).

In relation to extreme weather events, data services from weather services are also relevant. Available data are resolved in both spatial and temporal dimensions. However, references are not uniform and must be synchronised (see Figure 2). Depending on the weather phenomenon (heavy rain, heat waves, drought, storms etc.), the EU, for example, offers satellite-based data via the Copernicus Emergency Management System (EMS), on which current state data and forecasts with probabilities are calculated (Abily et al. 2020). These are available in frequencies from a few minutes to hours, relate to future time periods from minutes (precipitation) to months (drought)

and are resolved in the meter to kilometer range. The figure indicates these dimensions in layers. Parts of the EMS services are continuously available, others are activated and provided in a hazardous situation. Weather models are initially related to weather phenomena. With regard to flood situations, the European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) provides support; with regard to forest fires, the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) provides support; and with regard to soil drought, the European Drought Observatory (EDO) is to be consulted. Data are usually available in the form of geo-based raster data.

Figure 2 Consideration of global data, for example provided by national and European meteorological services.

The combination results in extreme data in terms of temporal and spatial resolution, field of view, sampling frequency and speed, heterogeneity of data formats, possible sources of error and interfering signals. The volume of data can be a challenge, but it is only one possible factor. Therefore, the term “big data” is avoided here in favour of “extreme data”.

Concept of uncertainty representation by Information Quality

Decision-makers at all levels of security management must be enabled to draw conclusions from this data. In the case of local data from sensor systems, the characteristic as “extreme data” results, for example, from the limited window of vision of the sensors that needs to be captured, diffuse environments with light and air conditions, the goodness of pre-processing algorithms and the mandatory communication channels. Global data can be obtained via the internet. Predictions are time- and space-related with probabilities. Availability is limited by licensing and legal restrictions and is partly controlled by private actors, so that not all actors may be able to act on a common data basis.

Uncertainty must therefore always be assumed. It can be represented in the form of information quality (IQ). Figure 3 shows a view from above of a geo-information system that visualises geo-based events detected in the data stream: If, for example, the detected data indicate a change in the anticipated forest fire front, the deployment of resources including sensor systems for data

collection - e.g. UAVs - must be re-planned. Event detection is one example of algorithms that process data and derive decision support from it. Another example is route planners based on machine learning.

Figure 3 Example scenario: Decision support based on global and local data (map sam-ple: Open-StreetMap)

The assessment of IQ will be based on Eppler's model (2006) (cf. (Pottebaum und Gräßler 2020; Moi et al. 2015)). It is based on a literature-based synthesis of different lists of dimensions, criteria and indicators. These are brought together under the following design dimensions:

- Allocation to phases of information processing from acquisition, verification, contextualisation to activation (cf. activities in the reconnaissance performed by actors in emergency response)
- Division into content and media (content is primarily shaped by relevance and credibility, media includes process and infrastructure)
- Differentiation into content, format and time dimension

This classification is chosen primarily because it focuses on the use of data and information (Pottebaum und Gräßler 2020). The "accuracy" of a date, for example, pays into relevance, is to be taken into account in the review phase and falls into the content dimension. The "timeliness" is a criterion for assessing credibility, is relevant at the time of activation and is in the time dimension. Accessibility is linked to infrastructure (possibly software-related), is important in the survey and belongs to the format dimension.

Depending on the type of uncertainty - expressed by a weakness in the IQ domain - decision-makers have to initiate different countermeasures or take them into account in the decision, for instance through a "plan B". For example, expert advisors may be called in to address weaknesses in content or to ensure credibility. The impact of weak accuracy, if any, can be assessed through sensitivity analyses. If data services are not accessible, a comparison with similar situations can

help to at least classify an acute situation. Figure 4 illustrates this concept using two different visualisation approaches.

Figure 4 Levels of information processing in CREXDATA with visualisation of IQ (based on (Eppler 2006))

First, the processing levels from data at the bottom to visualised information on top of the stack are shown, as they are built up in the CREXDATA project. Temperatures, videos, forest fire index and wind conditions are mentioned as examples of data. These are processed using methods such as classification by machine-trained models or Complex Event Forecasting (cf. (Pottebaum et al. 2012)). An “explainability layer” in the sense of eXplainable AI (XAI) adds information to enrich the results of this processing with additional information that is understandable to humans. This creates the basis for applying visualisation approaches. Shown on the left is a simple traffic light system that can be used to click through from the visualisation into the depth of the processing: On which layer and at which point is the uncertainty expressed by the yellow traffic light based? In this case, it could be unknown wind conditions that make a hazardous substance dispersion calculation uncertain. Shown on the right is a detailed representation based on IQ criteria (cf. (Eppler 2006)). Depending on the characteristics in the spider diagram, a recommendation can be offered as to which countermeasures would be useful to improve the IQ.

Implementation in CREXDATA

The CREXDATA project focuses on the algorithms and technical capabilities indicated by the above layers. They are based on efficient data acquisition and include processing close to the sensor, extraction of information and its visualisation. Explainability is a crucial interface that should be thought of by the use case. Instead of technical explainability, which can be created through targeted transparency of models, solutions are to be created in which decision-makers perceive a piece of information as “sufficiently explained”. The basis for the application in the field of hazard prevention is, on the one hand, rescue robotics (Kruijff-Korbayova et al. 2021) and, on the other hand, the geoinformation and decision support system ARGOS, which was built on the basis of results from the EU project ANYWHERE (Abily et al. 2020; van Lanen et al. 2019) (see Figure 5). ARGOS is used in different locations and levels of civil protection. Users include civil protection centrally in Spain, in Catalonia, in cities such as Badalona, but also in publicly or privately run institutions such as water management or the management of flood evacuation plans in campsites.

Thus, a functional basis is available to implement and test the described concepts in application scenarios.

Figure 5 ARGOS as an example of a weather-related decision support system (source: HYDS, <https://www.hyds.es/>)

Summary

CREXDATA experiments with different technologies from machine learning and Complex Event Recognition to Complex Event Forecasting, XAI and Visual Analytics to visualisation. The starting point is “extreme data”, which in this case includes local sensor data with different temporal and spatial resolutions and global data, e.g. from weather services. Interdependencies in terms of information quality are to be integrated into the situation visualisation and support the interpretation. This will extend existing foundations of information visualisation in terms of knowledge about uncertainty in extreme data. The results can be used in all forms of geo-based situation and command information systems.

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